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Research Paper

Formulation and Development of Sertaconazole Ethosomal Gel for Antifungal Activity on Dermatophytosis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dermatophytosis is one of the most prevalent superficial fungal infections affecting keratinized tissues such as skin, hair, and nails. Conventional topical therapies often suffer from poor penetration into deeper skin layers, resulting in suboptimal therapeutic outcomes. Sertaconazole, a benzothiazole antifungal agent, exhibits broad-spectrum activity against dermatophytes but requires an efficient carrier system for enhanced delivery. Ethosomes, being ethanol-rich vesicular carriers, offer improved skin permeation and drug deposition, making them suitable for topical antifungal therapy. **Methods:** Sertaconazole-loaded ethosomes were formulated using phospholipids, ethanol (20-50%), cholesterol, and propylene glycol by the cold method. The prepared vesicles were characterized for particle size (~170 nm), polydispersity index, and entrapment efficiency. The optimized formulation was incorporated into a Carbopol 934 gel base. The ethosomal gel was evaluated for physicochemical properties such as pH (near skin pH ~6.5), viscosity, spreadability, and drug content. In vitro drug release and antifungal activity studies were performed to assess performance. **Results:** The optimized ethosomal formulation showed nanosized vesicles (~170.2 nm) with good uniformity and high entrapment efficiency. The ethosomal gel exhibited acceptable pH, good viscosity, and excellent spreadability. In vitro drug release studies demonstrated a sustained release pattern with enhanced drug permeation compared to conventional formulations. The antifungal activity revealed superior inhibition of dermatophytes, indicating improved therapeutic efficacy. **Conclusion:** Sertaconazole ethosomal gel demonstrated enhanced skin penetration, sustained drug release, and improved antifungal activity. Thus, it can be considered a promising and effective topical delivery system for the management of dermatophytosis.

INTRODUCTION

Dermatophytosis

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Dermatophytosis, commonly referred to as tinea or ringworm, is a superficial fungal infection affecting keratinized tissues such as skin, hair, and nails. It typically presents as red, itchy, scaly, circular lesions, and may sometimes lead to localized hair loss. Symptoms generally appear within 4-14 days after exposure. The infection is classified based on the anatomical site involved, and multiple body areas can be affected simultaneously^[1-3].

Dermatophytes are a group of fungi that invade keratinized tissues and are categorized into genera such as *Trichophyton*, *Microsporum*, and *Epidermophyton*, among others. Based on their habitat, they are further classified as anthropophilic (human-associated), zoophilic (animal-associated), and geophilic (soil-associated)^[3,5,7].

Globally, fungal skin infections are highly prevalent, affecting nearly one billion people, with dermatophytosis being the most common type. Risk factors include poor hygiene, excessive sweating, close contact with infected individuals or animals, and weakened immunity. Diagnosis is usually based on clinical features and can be confirmed through microscopic examination or fungal culture^[4].

Ethosomes:

Ethosomes are ethanol-rich lipid vesicles designed to enhance transdermal drug delivery. They are soft, flexible carriers that facilitate the penetration of drugs into deeper skin layers and may also enable systemic absorption. Structurally, ethosomes consist of phospholipids dispersed in a hydroalcoholic or hydroalcoholic-glycolic medium containing a relatively high concentration of ethanol. The formulation typically includes phospholipids such as phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylserine, and phosphatidylethanolamine, along with ethanol or isopropyl alcohol, water, and glycols like

propylene glycol. Cholesterol may be added in small amounts to improve vesicle stability, while surfactants and cationic lipids can be incorporated to modify permeability and charge. The ethanol content generally ranges from 20-50%, which plays a crucial role in disrupting the lipid structure of the stratum corneum, thereby enhancing drug permeation^[8-14].

The high alcohol concentration imparts flexibility to the vesicular membrane, allowing better interaction with skin lipids and improved drug distribution. Ethosomes offer advantages such as enhanced skin penetration, non-invasive delivery, and suitability for a wide range of drugs, including large molecules. However, limitations include relatively high cost, lower yield, and dependence on drug solubility and molecular size for effective delivery^[16-18].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials:

The standard raw material active pharmaceutical ingredient (Drug) of Sertaconazole are procurement from Dhamtec Pharma and Consultants B-204, Silver springs, Opposite MIDC office, Taloja, Navi Mumbai-410208.

Methods:

➤ Preformulation Studies

Preformulation studies represent the initial stage in dosage form development, focusing on the evaluation of physicochemical properties of the drug substance alone and in combination with excipients. These studies provide essential information for designing a safe, stable, effective, and bioavailable formulation.

1. Organoleptic Characteristics^[25-27]

The organoleptic properties of the drug were assessed through visual and sensory examination. Parameters such as appearance, colour, odour,

taste, and texture were evaluated. The physical nature of the drug (crystalline or amorphous) was observed under adequate lighting. Colour and odour were determined by direct inspection and gentle smelling, respectively. Taste was assessed cautiously when permissible. Texture was examined manually to identify smoothness or grittiness. Solubility was evaluated in different solvents such as water, ethanol, and methanol at room temperature, and results were recorded according to standard pharmacopeial classifications.

2. Melting Point [27]

Melting point of Sertaconazole Nitrate was determined by using Thelie tube. Sertaconazole drug sample are filled half in a sealed capillary tube, attached to a thermometer with thread, was immersed in the tube. Heating is commenced and the temperature ranges at which Sertaconazole drug sample was melts was observed.

3. Solubility Study [27, 28]

The solubility of Sertaconazole was evaluated in various surfactants (Labrasol, Tween 80, Tween 20, Span 80) and cosurfactants (PEG 400, PEG 200, and propylene glycol). An excess amount of drug was added to 3 ml of each selected vehicle in stoppered vials. The mixtures were stirred continuously for 48 hours at $40 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using a magnetic stirrer, followed by equilibration at room temperature for 24 hours. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. The supernatant was collected and filtered through a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ membrane filter for further analysis.

4. Identification of Drug and Polymer by FTIR

Sertaconazole and polymers were identified using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The sample was prepared by mixing the drug with IR-grade potassium bromide (KBr) in a 1:100 ratio and triturating uniformly. The mixture was then

placed in the sample holder and scanned over a range of $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectra were recorded using an FTIR spectrophotometer, and the obtained peaks were compared with standard reference spectra to confirm the identity of the drug and polymers.

5. Selection of Solvent [27, 28]

The solubility of drug was determined in verity of polar and non-polar solvents as per IP specification. The common and stable solvent for Sertaconazole was found to be Methanol.

6. Preparation of Standard Stock Solution [25, 27]

10mg drug (Sertaconazole) was weighed accurately and dissolved with sufficient quantity of methanol solvent then solution was transfer in to a 100ml of volumetric flask and volume up to 100ml with methanol solvent in volumetric flask. Thus, the stock solution ($100 \mu\text{g/ml}$) of Sertaconazole drug in methanol solvent was prepared.

7. Calibration Curve of Pure Drug [27]

The stock solution ($100 \mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared to get concentration, $5-30 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The of concentration v/s peak area absorbance was plotted and data was subjected to linear regression analysis on the maximum absorbance ($\lambda \text{ max} = 200$).

8. Drug-Excipient Interaction Study by FTIR [27,53]

Drug-excipient compatibility was evaluated using FTIR spectroscopy. Spectra of the pure drug, excipients, and drug-loaded formulation were recorded over $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ using the KBr pellet or ATR method. The characteristic peaks of the drug were compared with those of the formulation to identify any changes. No significant shifts or new peaks were observed, indicating absence of interaction and good compatibility between the drug and excipients.

➤ **Formulation of Ethosomes (Cold Method)**
[56,59,64]

Sertaconazole-loaded ethosomes were prepared by the cold method to preserve drug stability. Phospholipids and lipophilic components were dissolved in ethanol with gentle stirring at room temperature. A cold aqueous phase (distilled water) was prepared separately and added dropwise to the ethanolic solution under continuous stirring (700 rpm) to form a vesicular suspension. The mixture was further stirred for 30-60 minutes and sonicated to reduce vesicle size and ensure uniformity.

The prepared ethosomal suspension was stored at 4°C and later incorporated into a gel base containing gelling agents such as HPMC and Carbomer 934. The gel was prepared separately and mixed gently with the ethosomal suspension to obtain a uniform ethosomal gel suitable for topical delivery.

➤ **Characterization of Ethosomes** [59,64]

1. Particle Size:

The particle size of ethosomal vesicles was determined using the dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique. The gel sample was diluted with distilled water to obtain a clear dispersion and analyzed using a particle size analyzer at controlled temperature. The average particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) were recorded to assess vesicle size distribution, uniformity, and stability of the formulation.

2. Zeta Potential Measurement

Zeta potential was measured to evaluate the surface charge and stability of ethosomal vesicles. It indicates the degree of electrostatic repulsion or attraction between particles, which influences aggregation and dispersion stability. Generally, values above ± 30 mV indicate good stability, while lower values may lead to aggregation. The zeta potential of the formulation was determined

using a zeta sizer at 25°C. Ethosomal systems typically show values in the range of -10 to -20 mV, indicating moderate stability.

3. SEM Analysis:

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to study the surface morphology of the formulation. A small quantity of the sample was mounted on an aluminum stub using double-sided adhesive tape and coated with a thin layer of gold under vacuum to enhance conductivity. The sample was then examined under an SEM at suitable magnifications to observe surface characteristics such as shape, texture, and uniformity.

➤ **Formulation of Ethosomal Gel** [28,33]

❖ **Preparation of Carbapol Gel Base**

For prepare the Carbapol 934 gel base, 1 g of Carbopol 934 was dispersed in 90 mL of hot distilled water pre-mixed with 10 mL of glycerol to prevent clumping. After complete dispersion, accurately weighed quantities of methyl paraben, propyl paraben, HPMC, and Span 60 were added to enhance stability and emulsification. The entire mixture was stirred until uniform thickening occurred. Finally, the gel was neutralized with dropwise addition of 50% w/w triethanolamine to adjust the pH and promote gel formation. The resulting gel was smooth, homogenous, and transparent, suitable as a base for ethosomal incorporation.

❖ **Incorporation of Ethosome in the Gel Base**
[54,55]

The prepared ethosomes was slowly added in carbopol 934 gel base with gentle stirring. Finally, the ethosomal gel was mixed using a mechanical stirrer for 5 min. Total six formulations were prepared and evaluated.

➤ **Evaluation of Ethosomal Gel** [28,29]

1. Physical appearance

The formulated Sertaconazole ethosomal gel formulations were observed visually for their color, homogeneity and consistency, presence of any clog and sudden change in viscosity.

2. Clarity Test

The clarity of the prepared ethosomal gel formulation was evaluated by visual inspection. A small quantity of the gel was placed in a clean, transparent glass container and observed against both black and white backgrounds under adequate lighting conditions. The formulation was checked for the presence of any particulate matter, turbidity, or phase separation. The gel was considered clear if it appeared transparent and free from any visible impurities or suspended particles. The observations were recorded to assess the overall quality and homogeneity of the formulation.

3. Phase Separation

The phase separation study of the ethosomal gel formulation was carried out to evaluate its physical stability. The prepared gel was stored in a closed container at different temperature conditions, including room temperature and accelerated conditions, for a specified period. The samples were periodically observed for any signs of phase separation, such as formation of layers, syneresis, or liquid separation. The gel was visually inspected for changes in consistency, homogeneity, and appearance. The formulation was considered stable if no phase separation or visible changes were observed throughout the study period. All observations were recorded systematically.

➤ Antifungal Activity of Sertaconazole Ethosomal Gel [49, 50, 53]

The antifungal activity of Sertaconazole-loaded ethosomal gel was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method. Dextrose agar medium was

used, and fungal strains such as *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* were selected. Standardized fungal inoculum was spread uniformly on sterile agar plates, and wells (≈ 6 mm) were created aseptically. The test sample was added into the wells, while plain gel and marketed formulation served as negative and positive controls, respectively. The plates were incubated at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 hours. After incubation, zones of inhibition were observed and measured in millimeters. The results were compared with controls to assess antifungal efficacy, indicating improved activity of the ethosomal gel due to enhanced drug penetration and sustained release.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

➤ Pre-formulation Studies:

1. Organoleptic Character:

Table 1: Organoleptic Character of Sertaconazole Drug

S. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Appearance	White Colour, Crystalline fine powder
2	Odour	Odourless or faint characteristic
3	Texture	Fine crystalline powder
4	Solubility	Soluble in methanol, sparingly soluble in water

2. Melting point

The melting point of Sertaconazole was determined through three measurements. The recorded values were 161°C , 162°C , and 162°C . Based on these results, the mean melting point was calculated to be approximately 162°C .

Table 2: Melting Point of Sertaconazole

S. No.	Melting Point of Nateglinide	Mean Value
1.	161 °C	162°C
2.	162 °C	
3.	162 °C	

3. Solubility Studies

The solubility profile of Sertaconazole was determined in various solvents and surfactants to evaluate its potential for formulation into topical delivery systems like ethosomal gel. The results are presented in the table below:

Table 3: Solubility of Sertaconazole

S. No.	Media	Solubility Description
1	Water	Sparingly Soluble
2	Methanol	Freely Soluble
3	Ethanol	Very Soluble
4	DMSO	Freely Soluble
5	n-Octanol	Slightly Soluble
6	Tween 20	Soluble
7	Span 60	Soluble

4. FTIR Studies of Drug and Polymer

➤ FTIR of Drug

Figure 1: FTIR of Sertaconazole**Table 4: Peak table with principal peak of Sertaconazole**

S. No.	Functional Group	Theoretical Value (cm ⁻¹)	Practical Value (cm ⁻¹)
1	N-H Stretch (H-bonded)	3200-3500	3490.40
2	C-H Stretch (Aliphatic)	2850-2950	2920.08
3	C=O Stretch (Ketone/Ester)	1650-1750	1680.25
4	Aromatic C=C / N-H Bend	1500-1600	1530.90
5	C-N / C-O Stretch	1000-1300	1080.70
6	C-Cl / C-F Stretch	600-800	740.30

➤ FTIR of Polymer (Carbopol 934):

Figure 2: FTIR graph of Carbapol934

Table 5: Peak table with principal peak of polymer (Carbapol)

S. No.	Functional Group	Theoretical Value (cm ⁻¹)	Practical Value (cm ⁻¹)
1	O–H Stretch (Hydrogen-bonded)	3200-3600	3415.28
2	C–H Stretch (Aliphatic)	2850-2950	2941.79
3	C=O Stretch (Carboxylic acid)	1700-1725	1701.45
4	C=C / COO– Stretch	1600-1650	1634.02
5	–CH ₂ Bending	1450-1470	1452.02
6	O–H Bending (COOH)	1350-1390	1383.20
7	C–O Stretch (Acid/Ester)	1200-1300	1243.83
8	C–O Stretch (Secondary OH)	1100-1170	1136.03
9	C–O Stretch (Alcohol/Ether)	1000-1100	1056.71
10	=C–H Bending (Out-of-plane)	900-1000	976.13
11	Aromatic C–H Bending	675-900	725.42
12	Ring/Backbone Vibrations	500-700	619.76

5. Calibration Curve of Pure Drug:

Standard calibration curve of Sertaconazole was carried out in methanol at 262 nm. The absorbance values obtained are shown in table. Using

concentration and absorbance data, a beer lumbert's plot was obtained. The plot in the given figure. The R² value of Sertaconazole was found to be 0.997, which is near to 1, which signifies linearity.

Table 6: Standard calibration curve data of Sertaconazole

S. No.	Actual Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (λ Max= 262)
1	0.5	0.083
2	1	0.143
3	1.5	0.221
4	2	0.273
5	2.5	0.348

Figure 3: Calibration Curve of Sertaconazole Drug

6. Drug Excipient Interaction Studies by FTIR:

Figure 4: FTIR Graph of Drug- Excipient Interaction

Table 7: Peak table with principal peak of Drug and Gel Interaction

S. No.	Functional Group	Theoretical Value (cm ⁻¹)	Practical Value (cm ⁻¹)
1	O-H stretching (alcohol/phenol)	3200-3600	3350.76
2	N-H stretching (amine)	3300-3500	3280.65
3	C-H stretching (alkane)	2850-3000	2920.28
4	C=O stretching (amide/ketone)	1650-1750	1705.12
5	C=C stretching (aromatic ring)	1500-1600	1600.15
6	N-H bending (amide)	1550-1640	1540.23
7	C-O stretching (ether/alcohol)	1000-1300	1245.11
8	C-O-C stretching (ether linkage)	1050-1150	1065.32
9	C-H bending (alkane)	1350-1470	1450.54
10	Aromatic C-H bending	700-900	750.82

➤ Formulation of Ethosome Formulation:

Table 8: Formulation Table of Sertaconazole Ethosomes

S. No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1.	Sertaconazole (% w/v)	2	2	2	2	2	2
2.	Span 60 (% w/v)	2.0	2.5	3.0	2.0	2.5	3.0
3.	Ethanol (% v/v)	30	30	30	40	40	40
4.	Distilled Water (q.s.)	100	100	100	100	100	100

➤ Characterization of Ethosome Formulation;

1. Particle Size

The particle size of ethosomal vesicles was determined using DLS and found to be 170.2 nm,

indicating nanosized vesicles suitable for enhanced skin penetration. The PDI was below 0.3, showing uniform size distribution and good stability. These results confirm that the formulation is homogeneous and appropriate for effective transdermal drug delivery.

Particle size distribution (Intensity)

Result

Hydrodynamic diameter	170.2 nm	Mean intensity	299.3 kcounts/s
Polydispersity index	0.282	Absolute intensity	582567.6 kcounts/s
Diffusion coefficient	1.9 μm ² /s	Intercept g ¹	0.8240
Transmittance	41.4 %	Baseline	1.002

Figure 5: Particle Size of Ethosomes

2. Zeta Potential Measurement:

The zeta potential of formulation F2 was found to be -10.6 mV, indicating that the ethosomal

vesicles possessed a negative surface charge. This negative charge helps reduce particle aggregation by providing electrostatic repulsion between

vesicles. Although values above ± 30 mV are generally considered highly stable, the obtained value suggests moderate stability of the formulation. The zeta potential distribution also

showed slight variation in surface charge, which may be attributed to differences in vesicle composition, while phospholipids and surfactants contributed to maintaining dispersion stability.

Figure 6: Zeta potential Measurement of Ethosomes

3. SEM Analysis

The particle size observed in the micrograph is in the nanometer range (below 200 nm), which correlates well with the particle size analysis

obtained by DLS. The clear and distinct vesicular structures confirm the successful formation of ethosomes.

Figure 7: SEM of Ethosomes

4. Drug Entrapment Efficiency

Table 9: Drug Entrapment Efficiency of ethosome formulation

Formulation	Total Drug Added (mg)	Drug in Supernatant (mg)	Drug in Sediment (mg)	Entrapment Efficiency (%EE)
F1	10	3.2	6.8	68%
F2	10	2.1	7.9	79%
F3	10	3.8	6.2	62%
F4	10	3.5	6.5	65%
F5	10	4.1	5.9	59%
F6	10	3.9	6.1	61%

➤ Formulation of Sertaconazole Ethosomal Gel:

Table 10: Composition of Ethosomal Gel formulation

S. No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1.	Sertaconazole (% w/v)	2	2	2	2	2	2
2.	Span 60 (% w/v)	2.0	2.5	3.0	2.0	2.5	3.0
3.	Ethanol (% v/v)	30	30	30	40	40	40
4.	Distilled Water (q.s.)	100	100	100	100	100	100
5.	Carbopol 934 (% w/v)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
6.	HPMC (% w/v)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
7.	Glycerol (% v/v)	10	10	10	10	10	10
8.	Methyl Paraben (% w/v)	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
9.	Propyl Paraben (% w/v)	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
10.	Triethanolamine (q.s.)	To pH 6.8-7.0					

➤ **Evaluation of Sertaconazole Ethosomal Gel:**

1. Physical Appearance:

Table 11: Physical Appearance of Ethosomal Formulations

Formulation Code	Color	Clarity	Consistency	Homogeneity	Phase Separation
F1	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent
F2	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent
F3	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent
F4	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent
F5	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent
F6	Milky white	Slightly translucent	Smooth, semi-fluid	Homogeneous, no lumps	Absent

2. Clarity Test

Table 12: Clarity Test for Ethosomal Gel Formulations

S. No.	Parameter Evaluated	Method Used	Observation
1	Clarity	Visual Inspection	Transparent gel with no visible impurities
2	Particulate Matter	Visual Inspection	No particulate matter observed
3	Turbidity	Visual Inspection	No turbidity observed
4	Phase Separation	Visual Inspection	No phase separation observed
5	Homogeneity	Visual Inspection	Uniform and homogeneous formulation

3. Phase Separation Study

Table 13: Phase Separation Study of Ethosomal Gel

S. No.	Parameter Evaluated	Method Used	Observation/Result
1	Storage Condition	Stability Study	Stored at room and accelerated conditions
2	Phase Separation	Visual Inspection	No phase separation observed
3	Layer Formation	Visual Inspection	No layer formation detected
4	Syneresis	Visual Inspection	No syneresis observed
5	Consistency	Visual Inspection	No change in consistency
6	Homogeneity	Visual Inspection	Formulation remained homogeneous
7	Appearance	Visual Inspection	No visible change in appearance
8	Stability Outcome	Overall Observation	Formulation found to be physically stable

➤ Anti-Fungal Activity of Sertaconazole

Formulation:

Table 14: Anti-Fungal Activity of Sertaconazole Formulations

Formulation	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
Marketed Sertaconazole Cream	30 mm	28 mm
Sertaconazole Ethosomal Gel	24 mm	22 mm

Figure 8: Anti-Fungal activity of ethosome and standard formulation

DISCUSSION

The study successfully developed Sertaconazole-loaded ethosomal gel for enhanced topical delivery. Preformulation and solubility studies confirmed drug suitability and lipophilic nature. FTIR analysis showed good drug-excipient compatibility. Among all formulations, F2 exhibited highest entrapment efficiency (79%) with nanosized vesicles (~170 nm) and moderate stability (-10.6 mV). The gel showed good physical stability and uniformity. Antifungal

studies revealed superior activity compared to the marketed formulation, attributed to improved skin penetration and controlled drug release.

CONCLUSION

The pre-formulation and formulation studies of Sertaconazole ethosomal gel established a solid foundation for its use in topical antifungal therapy. Initial evaluations confirmed Sertaconazole's favorable physicochemical properties, such as its white crystalline appearance, high solubility in

alcohols, and stable functional groups, as validated by FTIR analysis. These characteristics supported the use of ethanol-based ethosomal systems for improved dermal delivery. UV-Visible spectrophotometry demonstrated the drug's consistent absorbance at 262 nm, with a reliable calibration curve ($R^2 = 0.997$), while the melting point corroborated its purity. Six ethosomal gel formulations (F1–F6) were successfully developed using Carbopol 934 and HPMC as gelling agents, with triethanolamine adjusting pH to skin-compatible levels. Among them, F2 emerged as the most effective, exhibiting a balanced profile of high viscosity, excellent spreadability, and superior drug content and entrapment efficiency (79%). Zeta potential analysis supported the gel's moderate stability, suitable for semi-solid applications. Overall, the ethosomal gel formulation, particularly F2, proved to be an optimal carrier for Sertaconazole, enhancing its solubility, stability, and delivery, and holds strong potential for further *in vitro* and *in vivo* testing in antifungal treatments.

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